

OBTAINING OF COMPOSITES BASED ON ELASTOMERS, OLIGOMERS AND BITUMEN FILLED WITH ORGANIC AND INORGANIC FILLERS

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Abstract

Currently, preference is given to research aimed at obtaining, researching and using composites for various purposes from compounds obtained as a result of their modification, in order to eliminate the disadvantages of existing macromolecules produced on an industrial scale, and is distinguished by its relevance [1-6]. In the research work, the epoxy-diane oligomer was first modified with oxamide, its main indicators were determined, and then a target composition was developed on its basis. When preparing the composition, a modified epoxy-diane oligomer was used as a binder.

Keywords: epoxy resin, oxamide, modification, composite, filler, bitumen, elastomer.

Introduction

In the course of the study, 20-40 m.f. (mass fraction) bitumen of the Baku 85/25 brand with a softening temperature $T_{\text{soft}} = 60-70$ °C, 1-3 m.f butadiene-nitrile elastomer of the SCN-40 brand, 5-10 m.f. cooligomer was taken, and magnesium oxide and 3-5 m.f. of pomgranate bark powder were used as a filler. Acetone was used as a solvent. The aim of the work is to develop and research areas of application of composites based on relatively environmentally friendly compounds (elastomeric, so-oligomeric and bituminous). SCN-40 butadiene-nitrile was used as an elastomer, epoxy-diane oligomer, modified with oxamide for the first time, was used as a co-oligomer, and Baku 85/25 bitumen was used as bitumen. Due to the addition of filler to the composite made on the basis of a three-component system, its physical, mechanical and operational parameters have increased, and the cost price has decreased. Due to the low penetration temperature, elasticity and

softening, which are considered the main indicators of Baku 85/25 bitumen containing 8% paraffin (in fact, no more than 2-3%, its modification is also provided to improve its main indicators), the basic physical, mechanical and operational indicators of the composite are low. In order for the main indicators of a composite made on the basis of a three-component system to be high, first of all, it is necessary to develop a target composite, having previously eliminated the shortcomings of each of them separately. The epoxy-diane cooligomer functionalized with oxamide positively affected the adhesion ability, heat resistance, elasticity and other indicators of the system. This cooligomer was used as a binder, and a composite coating was developed [7-9].

Methodology

The main parameters of the epoxy-diane cooligomer modified with oxamide have been studied [11-12].

Table 1.

Main indicators of the epoxy-diane co-oligomer modified with oxamide

№	Indicators	Epoxy-diane oligomer	Modified epoxy-diane cooligomer
1.	Density, kg/m ³	1110	1145
2.	Number of epoxy groups, %	16	8.6
3.	Softening temperature using the Ubbelohde thermometer, °C	75	95
4.	Degree of solidification, within 5 hours at 150 °C	96	98
5.	Molecular weight	390-480	890-1000
6.	Relative viscosity in the VZ-4 device, sec.	48	52
7.	Adhesive strength, MPa	2.2	2.8

The IR spectrum of an epoxy-diane co-oligomer modified with oxamide has been studied (Fig. 1). It turned out from the spectrum that the peak of $3582.86-3381.89$ cm⁻¹ corresponds to the valence vibrations of the -OH and -NH

Figure 1. IR spectrum of the epoxy-diane cooligomer modified with oxamide

The IR spectrum of an epoxy-diane co-oligomer modified with oxamide has been studied (Fig. 1). It turned out from the spectrum that the peak of 3582.86-3381.89 cm^{-1} corresponds to the valence vibrations of the -OH and -NH bond, 2922.31 -2725.72 cm^{-1} corresponds to the deformation vibrations of the -CH group, 1651.58-1605.53 cm^{-1} corresponds to the valence vibrations of the C=C benzene ring bond, 1455.22-1378.13 cm^{-1} -CH₂ and -CH 1169.41-1009.0 cm^{-1} peak groups -OH and CH=CH, 936.56-826.84 cm^{-1} peak deformation groups CH=CH₂, 721.98 -665.78 cm^{-1} peak

valence oscillations of groups belonging to the C-Cl bond.

From the curve of DTA and TGA of the epoxy-diane co-oligomer modified with oxamide (Fig.2), it can be seen that the mass loss during thermal destruction amounted to 6.45% at the initial stage of destruction, 16.39% at the next second stage and, finally, 43.9% at the third stage. At the same time, at the last stage, a weakening of the thermal destruction process was observed and the amount of energy consumed decreased.

Figure 2. Analysis of DT and TG of the epoxy-diane co-oligomer modified with oxamide

Main part

The main indicators of the destruction process are given in Table 2. It turned out that at the first stage of the process of thermo-oxidative destruction, the product of destruction is water, and at the second stage new

low-molecular compounds formed due to the selected functional groups. At the third stage, there is an intensive dehydrogenation process, and as a result, coke is obtained.

Table 2.

Indicators of the process of thermal destruction of the modified epoxy-diane cooligomer

№	Indicators	Unit of measurement	Quantity
1.	The temperature of the beginning of destruction	°C	123.2
2.	Weight loss at stage I	%	6.43
3.	Weight loss at stage II	%	16.39
4.	Weight loss at stage III	%	43.9
6.	Semi-decay temperature	°C	425
7.	Coke number	%	29.21

Obtaining of the composition based on elastomer, co-oligomer and bitumen was carried out for 1.0-1.5 hours under conditions of intensive mixing at 50-55 °C.

The composition and main indicators of the multicomponent composite are given in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3.

Composition of the composite

№	Bitumen of the Baku 85/25 brand, m.f.	Functionalized cooligomer, m.f.	Butadiene-nitrile elastomer, m.f.	Filler, m.f.	Solvent, ml
I	20	5.0	1.0	3.0	35
II	30	7.5	2.0	4.0	35
III	40	10	3.0	5.0	35

Table 4.

The main indicators of the composite

Examples	Softening temperature, °C	Elongation, cm	Penetration, mm
I	60	66	15
II	63	72	12
III	65	75	10

A modified epoxy-diane oligomer was used as a binder for comparison. As the hardening temperature of a multicomponent composite increases, its basic physical, mechanical and operational parameters also increase. The higher the content of acrylonitrile in the butadiene-nitrile elastomer, the faster the solidification process goes, that is, the process of chemical modification between functional groups occurs. Feeding the filler into the system leads to an increase in its viscosity. To prepare the coating composition from a three-component system, elastomer, cooligomer and bitumen are first dissolved separately in an organic solvent, mixed and gradually added to a suitable filler system,

continuously mixing the mixture of components for 1.0 h. The finished composition is applied to a pre-cleaned metal surface in two layers 50-60 microns thick. The solidification process takes place in the following mode:

- 80 °C - 0.5 hours
- 100 °C - 0.5 hours
- 120 °C - 1.0 hours
- 140 °C - 4 hours

Findings

The physicomachanical parameters of the composite coating after the curing process were studied (Table 5).

Table 5.

The main indicators of the composite based on elastomer, cooligomer and bitumen

Indicators	Composites based on elastomers, oligomers and bitumen	Composites based on elastomers, cooligomers and bitumen
Impact resistance, kg/cm	32	38
Resistance to bending, mm	3.0	5.0
Adhesive strength, MPa	18	26
Conditional viscosity, sec	48	56
Hardness in a conventional unit	0.75	0.95
Swelling, at 20 °C for 30 days, %	4-5	-

Table 5 shows that the cross-linked three-dimensionally constructed composite has high physical, mechanical and operational characteristics. The processes of destruction of composites on the basis of elastomers, cooligomers and bitumen have also been studied (Fig.3). The process of thermal destruction by differential thermal (DT) and thermogravimetric (TG) analysis is a very sensitive method and requires high accuracy. During the study, it becomes obvious that with the gradual heating of the sample, changes occur during the separation of heat (exothermic) and absorption (endothermic). Table 6 shows that the process of thermal destruction of the composition of the coating based on elastomer, sooligomer and bitumen is also a step-by-step process. From the analysis of the DT and TG composite based on elastomer, oligomer and bitumen, it became known that the process of thermal destruction of a multicomponent composite begins at 240 °C, and the mass loss at the same time amounted to 4.08%. At the next stage, i.e. at 362 °C, the mass loss was 13.68%, and at 453.5 °C, the mass loss was 60.85%.

Figure 3. DT and TG analysis of composite based on elastomer, cooligomer and bitumen

Table 6.

The main indicators of the process of thermal destruction of the composite coating

№	Indicators	Unit of measurement	Quantity
1.	The temperature of the beginning of destruction	°C	143.0
2.	Weight loss at stage I	%	4.08
3.	Weight loss at stage II	%	13.68
4.	Weight loss at stage III	%	60.85
5.	Semi-decay temperature	°C	458
6.	Coke number	%	22.91

From the process of thermal destruction of the multicomponent composition of the coating, it can be seen that compared with the process of thermal destruction of the cooligomer, its heat resistance is higher. The degree of solidification of epoxy-diane cooligomers modified with oxamide at different temperatures and at different times was also studied (Table 7).

Table 7.

Degree of solidification of the cooligomer (α) at different temperatures (T) and time (τ)

№	Curing temperature, °C									
	110		120		130		140		150	
	τ , min	α , %	τ , min	α , %	τ , min	α , %	τ , min	α , %	τ , min	α , %
1	60	86.80	60	87.80	60	87.98	60	89.23	60	90.28
2	120	90.43	120	90.61	120	92.14	120	93.18	120	94.22
3	180	91.85	180	92.77	180	93.27	180	94.26	180	95.34
4	240	93.49	240	93.64	240	94.66	240	94.78	240	95.57
5	300	93.86	300	94.53	300	94.89	300	95.71	300	96.68

The table shows that the maximum solidification rate of the cooligomer is 97% at 150 °C for 5 h. The curing process takes place in the presence of functional groups and temperature.

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